

Historical mining towns: The establishment of ‘Soil Planning Areas’ for the risk management of contaminated soil

Soili Solismaa^{a,*}, Kirsti Loukola-Ruskeeniemi^b, Kristiina Nuottimäki^b, Hanna Tolvanen^c, Kimmo Järvinen^c, Ingo Müller^d

^a Geological Survey of Finland, P.O. Box 1237, Kuopio FI-70211, Finland

^b Geological Survey of Finland, P.O. Box 96, Espoo FI-02151, Finland

^c Ramboll Finland Oy, Itsehallintokuja 3, Espoo 02600, Finland

^d Saxon State Office for Environment, Agriculture and Geology, Halsbrückerstr. 31a, Freiberg 09599, Germany

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ABSTRACT

Historical mining towns face financial challenges with the proposed Soil Monitoring Law of the European Union, which will require the management of soil contamination, since remediating soil in densely populated towns and cities is challenging.

We compared the environmental impact of sulfide ore mining in the urban area of Outokumpu in Finland with that of other European sites, focusing on soil contamination. Soil sampling revealed that mine tailings were historically used in road construction. The threshold values of Cu, Ni, and Zn were exceeded at several points, with the highest Cu content reaching 2733 mg/kg. Groundwater and surface water contamination was also evident, mainly due to the lack of a proper protective structure in tailings to prevent acid mine drainage. A preliminary risk assessment suggests health risks from unintentional soil ingestion and dust inhalation. However, the issues in many historical mining towns are more severe if they contain high levels of As or Pb which are more toxic than those of concern in Outokumpu.

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: soili.solismaa@gtk.fi (S. Solismaa).

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The historical mining town of Freiberg in Saxony, Germany, has been regulated as a 'Soil Planning Area', where limit values have been provided based on land use scenarios. The regional handling and re-use of excavated soil is based on contamination categories, with the tightest restrictions for the areas where the As content exceeds 340 mg/kg. We suggest 'Soil Planning Areas' to be established in historical mining towns facing similar challenges as a first step to mitigate environmental and health risks with reasonable economic resources.

1. Introduction

1.1. Background

Worldwide, there are some 160,000 abandoned mines, and over 20 million people live on floodplains affected by past or present metal mining [1]. Mining and metallurgical industries have contaminated soil, surface water, and groundwater especially during past centuries as mineral extraction and processing were not as effective as today and the management of mining wastes was not regulated. A common procedure was that waste rock piles and tailings dams consisting of a mixture of solids and liquids were left on site. Mining wastes were reported to contaminate rivers as early as 7000 years ago [2].

Thousands of past and present mining sites across the globe have been identified through the visual interpretation of satellite images for above-ground mining features such as open cuts, tailings, waste rock dumps, waste ponds, and processing infrastructure [3]. However, some historical mine sites can no longer be recognized in satellite images. In addition to the sites of ancient mining and metallurgical industries nowadays situated in relatively pristine areas, they may exist in the middle of densely populated areas, where old tailings, waste rock piles, and contaminated soil are located under streets and in parks, gardens, and playgrounds.

The local population has typically increased during mining activities. While some mining towns were practically abandoned when the ores had been mined out, many old mining towns are at present populated, and other livelihoods have replaced the employment once provided by the local mining industry. The contamination inherited from past mining and metallurgical plants may cause risks to human health and the environment. Inhaling dust particles containing toxic metals is a significant exposure route, especially in arid and semiarid areas. Street dust in a city close to a mine site may have inherited its contaminant composition from the tailings area [4]. In addition to human health, past mining has harmful impacts on the environment. For example, the wildlife in some protected areas in France is suffering due to contaminated topsoil resulting from ancient mining activities [5], and mining areas may pose an ecological risk to plants and soil-consuming organisms via soil particle-induced ecotoxicity [6].

Old mining towns constitute a challenge in the execution of several existing national regulations on contaminated sites and the proposed Soil Monitoring Law of the European Union, which requires that Member States manage soil contamination [7]. Jordan [8] summarized that a significant proportion of sites with contaminated soil and water are associated with historical mining in Europe, and Panagos et al. [9] estimated that around 7% of the contaminated sites in Europe result from mining activities. Inhabited historical mining towns require special care due to the risks of soil degradation [10-13]. In addition to contaminated soil and mining residues, groundwater and surface waters have been contaminated, not to mention the higher-than-average natural geochemical background levels of contaminants in mining districts even before any mining operations commenced. It is challenging to retrospectively distinguish naturally high geochemical background levels of metals from mining-induced contamination.

Poorly executed mine closure contributes to ecological and human health risks, as well as safety issues, and can adversely affect communities and lead to environmental, social, and economic disadvantages (e.g., [4,6]). Previous activities and measures, today known to be inadequate, can subsequently be addressed by remediating the contaminated

areas. Hou et al. [14] divide conventional remediation methods for all types of brownfield sites into five main approaches: (i) excavation and off-site disposal of contaminated soils (dig and haul), (ii) groundwater remediation (pump and treat), (iii) thermal desorption of the soil contaminants, (iv) chemical treatment of contaminated soil or water, and (v) solidification and stabilization of contaminated soil. Conventional methods usually have some disadvantages, making them unsuitable for large areas. They may disturb the soil structure and biota of the site (e.g., [15]) and result in substantial expenses, such as costs related to the transportation of contaminated soils, disposal fees, or the establishment and monitoring of disposal sites, as well as the use of extraction methods, chemicals, and cement. Furthermore, greenhouse gas emissions due to transportation and the use of cement as a stabilizing agent need to be considered.

Hou et al. [14] suggest utilizing modern sustainable remediation techniques. These strategies were selected based on their mature technology and include i) sustainable immobilization using cement-free binders, ii) low-impact bioremediation, iii) new *in situ* chemical treatment, and iv) innovative barrier systems. Nature-based brownfield remediation solutions include the conversion of brownfields to urban parks and industrial heritage parks. Additionally, Niblick and Landis [16] suggest utilizing brownfield sites for producing sustainable biofuel and wind and solar energy.

One of the environmental disadvantages caused by both historical and current mining activities is acid mine drainage (AMD) (e.g., [17]). The extraction of sulfide ores may cause the oxidation of sulfide minerals, which produces sulfuric acid and leads to the leaching of potentially toxic metals and/or metalloids, such as copper, nickel, zinc, cobalt, chromium, cadmium, lead, antimony, and arsenic, to the surrounding environment (e.g., [18-20]). The quantities of released elements and compounds depend on the mineralogy and chemical characteristics of the ore deposit, the extraction methods, and the environmental protection and monitoring activities performed. If sufficient protective structures are lacking and seepage water collection and treatment are inadequate, AMD can continue to transport harmful substances to the environment for decades, and in the Arctic for centuries.

A representative and widely accepted term to describe the contaminants released as a consequence of sulfide ore extraction is still lacking. The terms trace metals, heavy metals, and potentially toxic elements (PTE) are inadequate to describe the whole spectrum of AMD-derived pollutants, since AMD also generates compounds such as sulfates and creates acidity, which are not included in any of these terms. The acidity, metals (e.g., Cu, Co, Ni, Zn, and Cr), metalloids (e.g., As and Sb), sulfate (SO_4^{2-}), and other harmful compounds form and spread into the environment during and after sulfide ore mining and extraction. These are collectively referred to in this paper as 'sulfide ore extraction-related contaminants', abbreviated as SOEC.

Numerous research projects in the EU, such as the MIREU project (<https://mireu.eu/>), have investigated historical mining regions and their environmental impacts. The recent EU Horizon project ISLANDR 'Information-based strategies for land remediation' (2023-2026) is one of the Soil Mission projects. The historical Cu-Co-Zn mining town of Outokumpu in Finland is one of the ISLANDR test areas, representing historical mining towns of Europe in the project. Outokumpu is the only sulfide ore mining site in Finland where the tailings areas and waste rock piles are located inside the town [21].

1.2. Aim and objectives

The specific research questions are as follows:

- 1) Environmental and health issues exist in historical mining towns resulting from former mining activities. Have these issues been mitigated through previous measures in the mining towns selected for comparison?
- 2) Which types of soil data are usually available from the historical mining sites? Are the data gathered sufficient for environmental and health risk analyses and the planning of remediation measures and other risk management actions? The studies carried out in the mining town of Outokumpu are presented as an example.

- 3) Can we find solutions to manage the extensive soil contamination in historical mining towns that are both economically viable and environmentally responsible?
- 4) Can a 'Soil Planning Area' risk management procedure developed in Germany for the mining town of Freiberg be applied as a first step in other countries?

Here, we present the history and current state of soil and water contamination in the center of Outokumpu. Previously, SOEC-rich mine tailings were used in road construction, which is now causing challenges, since these roads have reached the end of their service life and require reconstruction. Preliminary risks of SOEC-rich soil to the environment and human health were assessed for both current and planned land use.

Fig. 1. Locations of selected historical mining towns in Europe. Outokumpu, Falun, Freiberg, Aljustrel, and Lavrio are marked with star symbols.

We compared our findings from Outokumpu with six historical mining towns and cities (Fig. 1), namely Freiberg in Germany, Falun in Sweden, Aljustrel in Portugal, and Lavrion in Greece, and two examples from other continents: Tocopilla in Chile [22] and Daye in China [23], aiming to identify reasonable risk management tools to remediate soil in cities with a mining history. This type of comparison and discussion has not been reported before. The Freiberg mining area has been regulated as a 'Soil Planning Area', providing different means to address issues such as the relocation of contaminated soils, transfer of contaminants to crops in agricultural land, and human intake of contaminants in playgrounds or residential areas (e.g., [24,25]).

In the following sections, we first present the results from Outokumpu to give the reader an idea of the expensive challenges mining towns will be facing with modern environmental legislation. We discuss the remediation options, considering the principles of the circular economy and comprehensive improvement of the surrounding environment.

2. Materials and methods

The history of the environmental impacts of mining at Outokumpu presented here and a comparison with the selected historical mining towns of Freiberg in Germany, Falun in Sweden, Aljustrel in Portugal, and Lavrion in Greece, as well as Tocopilla in Chile and Daye in China were based on a literature study. In this paper, we report the results of soil and water sampling performed at Outokumpu and a preliminary risk assessment based on these results. Finally, we present a proposal for the disposal and/or utilization of SOEC-rich soil in Outokumpu, which could be considered in mining towns worldwide struggling with similar challenges.

Environmental studies concerning the mining wastes used in road construction in the Outokumpu urban area were conducted by Ramboll Finland during 2021 and 2022. The study area covered approximately 12 km² in Outokumpu town center. The survey was commissioned by the town of Outokumpu and the Pirkanmaa Centre for Economic Development, Transport, and the Environment (PIRELY) to assess the extent of use of mine tailings as a construction material and to assess the risks to the environment and human health within the town area based on the current and planned land use. Two reports by PIRELY are available in Finnish [26,27]. A total of 80 soil sampling points were established within the town center, either as excavated test pits (19) or drilling points (61). The test pits reached a depth of 1.5–2.0 m, and three to four samples were collected from each pit according to the soil layers present. Altogether, 69 soil samples were collected from the test pits. The drilling points reached depths of 2.5–3.0 m, and three to four samples were collected from different soil layers and depths based on the soil layers present. Altogether, 211 soil samples were collected from the drilled sampling points.

Laboratory analyses were performed for 36 test pit samples and 132 drill core samples. Samples for which the concentration measured with a portable X-ray fluorescence (pXRF) device (Olympus Innov-X) for any of the elements mentioned in the [28] exceeded the lower guideline value (see Appendix B) were selected for laboratory analysis. If none of the samples in a test pit or drilling point exceeded this value, one to two samples were randomly sent for laboratory analysis. *Aqua regia* digestion was performed using microwave-assisted extraction for dried (40°C overnight) and sieved (<2 mm) soil samples to measure the acid-extractable content of metals and metalloids. After the extraction, the samples were filtered and diluted for analysis with inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometry (ICP-AES). *Aqua regia* effectively digests sulfides, saline minerals, trioctahedral micas, clay minerals, secondary precipitates, and certain Mg and Ca silicates [29, 30].

The water sampling included groundwater, household well water, and runoff water samples from the urban area of Outokumpu. Groundwater samples were collected from five groundwater monitoring wells in

November 2021 and March 2022. One of the monitoring wells was located outside the study area and represented the chemical background concentrations. Household well water samples (12) that were not used for potable water were collected from six dug wells and bore wells in November 2021 and March 2022. Three runoff water samples were collected from ditches in the study area in November 2021. Analysis of basic water quality parameters (pH, conductivity, hardness, and oxygen concentration) was conducted in an accredited laboratory for all water samples. In addition, the soluble content of the water samples was determined with the ICP-MS method according to the EN ISO 17294-2 certificate. The results were compared with surface water results from previous studies, especially regarding the transportation of contaminants.

Based on the analytical results for samples of soil, dust, tap water, and edible plants, a preliminary risk assessment was conducted concerning the human health risks caused by the SOEC-containing soil material in the center of Outokumpu. The soil samples were collected during 2021–2022 by Ramboll Finland. Dust and tap water results were adopted from previous studies performed by Groundia Oy [31] and average metal contents from municipal assessment results regarding tap water quality in Outokumpu between 2010–2020. Only two plant species and one fungus species (four berry samples and one fungus sample) were used. Due to the limited availability of edible plants and outdated results of dust, the risk assessment result is only indicative. The risk assessment followed the principles and calculation methods presented and well documented by United States Environmental Protection Agency [32,33]. This approach was chosen since it is commonly used in human health risk assessment [34–37,23], it is the recommended human health risk approach in Finland [38], and it therefore offers comparability with other human health risk assessments in Finland and internationally. The strengths of this model are that it can be utilized in various climates, for populations with different diets, and it is well suited to several different contaminants, as long as sufficient toxicological data are available. The application of this method to real case studies has produced results that can be readily utilized by risk managers. The downsides include the ever-present differences between the default values used in risk assessment and their representativeness of the real individuals under assessment, since there are always variations in diet, body weight, background exposure, sample representativeness, and metabolism between the default example and real individuals. The human health risk should not be taken literally, but considered as a tool for risk management. This is, however, the nationally adopted approach to risk assessment in Finland, although the guidelines are not binding. Calculations were performed using maximum values, average values, and median values for contaminants detected in each medium for comparison.

The exposure of people living in the Outokumpu study area to the identified contaminants has been calculated for each relevant exposure route and contaminant separately as an average daily dose (ADD) [39], and total exposure for an individual (both adults and children considered in the calculation) is then summed from singular exposure route results and compared with the tolerable daily intake (TDI) value for each contaminant considered in the assessment [40]. The TDI is an element- or compound-specific maximum acceptable daily intake per kg body weight of an individual. Sometimes marking reference dose (RfD) is used instead. Accepted default values from the publication are used when exact data are unavailable or producing such data is difficult (e.g., daily intake of fungi, fish, berries, soil; weight of an individual; daily water intake by drinking). The result of dividing ADD_{tot} by TDI is called a hazard quotient (HQ) [41]. A hazard quotient expresses the ratio of a single contaminant to a reference dose of the contaminant received by an individual over a similar time period to what the reference dose is defined for. When HQ > 1 for a non-carcinogenic contaminant, it triggers a further need for assessing in detail the health or ecological risk to individuals exposed to this contaminant and possibly some risk management actions that should be considered. This approach is defined by

the United States Environmental Protection Agency [42,43] and commonly used in risk assessments or national guidelines [34-36,38,37, 42,23].

$$ADD_i = (C_i \times IR \times EF \times ED)/(BW \times AT) \quad (1)$$

where, ADD_i = average daily dose for singular exposure route [mg/kg-d], C_i = representative concentration of a contaminant in the observed media in the study area (soil, air, water, sediment, food [mg/kg, mg/L, or mg/m³]), IR = ingestion / inhalation rate, i.e., the daily intake of a contaminant-containing medium through the observed exposure route [kg/d, L/d, or m³/d], EF = exposure frequency as [d/a], ED = exposure duration as [a], BW = body weight of an exposed individual, AT = averaging time, i.e., the time over which the average daily dose is calculated

$$ADD_{tot} = ADD_1 + ADD_2 \dots ADD_n \quad (2)$$

$$HQ = ADD_{tot}/TDI \quad (3)$$

If several contaminants are present that have additive effects on the exposed subject (for example, several contaminants having adverse effects on the lungs when inhaled), the risk is described using a hazard index (HI). This is calculated by adding the hazard quotients for the selected contaminants and exposure route [18]. The hazard index should not exceed 1 [18].

The exposure routes that were assessed in the preliminary risk assessment for the Outokumpu study area by Ramboll Finland included human exposure through ingestion and inhalation. The general assumptions used in the risk assessment are presented in Appendix A.

The combined effects of exposure to SOEC through these exposure routes were also assessed. Direct skin contact with soil was not considered to be an exposure pathway. Calculations were performed for both children and adults alike, and areas where exposure was seen as possible were areas near the roads in the town center and in the new planning areas, which are largely intended to be residential areas, but also areas for workplaces and public services. Exposure by inhalation was considered to occur through inhaling dust particles in the study area. The calculated SOEC concentrations in the PM10 particle-size dust were compared with the respective TCA values, which describe the highest concentration level without adverse effects.

The additive effect of exposure to SOEC was calculated for Co, Cr, Ni, and Zn in dust, since they all affect the respiratory tract and are reported to have negative health effects in the lungs when inhaled [39,44-48]. The hazard index (HI) for the combined effect was calculated using the hazard quotients from the ingestion exposure route.

3. Results

3.1. Studies at Outokumpu

3.1.1. History of soil and water contamination at Outokumpu

The Outokumpu mining district hosts several polymetallic Cu–Co–Zn–Ni–Ag–Au sulfide deposits (Fig. 2a). Metamorphosed black shales envelop the so-called Outokumpu rock assemblage, containing serpentinite and Ca–Si-rich rocks, in addition to sulfide deposits and occurrences [49,50]. The exploited sulfide ores include the historical Outokumpu mines known as Kumpu, Mökkivaara, and Keretti, located in the town center of Outokumpu (Fig. 2b), as well as the Vuonos mine, 7 km northeast, the Kylylahti mine, 25 km northeast, and the Lui-konlahti mine, 27 km northwest. In this study, we focused on the environmental consequences of the mines located in the vicinity of the town center. The mining activities in the town took place from 1910 to 1989, with a total amount of extracted ore of 32 Mt, of which 9.5 Mt ended up in the mine tailings [21]. In addition to the mines located in the town, the Vuonos mine has caused environmental impacts on Lake Sismjärvi. The Vuonos Cu–Zn–Ni–Co–S mine operated from 1967 to

1986, and 15.6 Mt of ore was extracted. The mine tailings impoundment at Vuonos serves at present as a disposal site for mine tailings from talc ore processing [51]. Talc is an alteration product of serpentinite.

Between 1913 and 1929, the extractive wastes and sulfur dioxide-containing flue gases of the Outokumpu mine and the metallurgical copper factory were released directly into the environment, a strategy applied for centuries in mining and processing around the world [53]. The first Kumpu mine practiced small-scale mining. The mine tailings were placed near the enrichment plant, which is part of the current mining museum area. The mine tailings area was later covered and landscaped, but water infiltration continued through the cover, followed by sulfide oxidation, leading to AMD. In addition, the waste rocks remain partially uncovered [21]. The mine tailings of the Mökkivaara mine were, together with the process water, released as a slurry to a pond in the valley known as Outolampi (MT1 in Fig. 2b), which acted as a clarification pond for the solid waste. Mine tailings settled to the bottom of the pond and the water clarified from solids was directed to the watercourse without purification. Acid SOEC-rich water flowed through the uncovered bottom of the naturally formed pond and through the inadequate dam structures, which collapsed and caused groundwater pollution in the 1940s [53]. Within the same time frame, the mine tailings, containing on average 18 % S, were placed as fillings in empty mine cavities, and the ore pillars that were earlier left to support the cavities were mined and utilized [54].

Contaminated water flowed from the mine tailings area to natural ponds and the River Ruutunjoki [55]. This river flows to Lake Sismjärvi, which is located 5 km southeast of the mine (Fig. 2a). Lake Sismjärvi was acidified and polluted and became unviable until 1943 [53]. The acid SOEC-rich water also flowed through the permeable sandy and silty soil at the bottom of the Outolampi pond, contaminating groundwater between the tailings pond and Lake Sismjärvi [56]. A visible iron precipitate formed in places where groundwater was discharged to the surface of the ground [56]. A new mine, Keretti (1954–1989), continued to release slurry mining wastes to MT1 (Fig. 2b), and later to the esker kettle located on the northern side of MT2 and to the MT3 waste area [21].

The mine began to process the so-called waste ore in the 1950s, when sulfur concentrate became economically viable. Although this was an act of circular economy, the environmental impacts were not addressed, and dusting became a problem. The enrichment of the extractive waste continued in the 1960s to recover Cu, Co, and S with a more advanced flotation method. This operation from time to time required the removal of upper depleted layers, around 20 000 m³ of which were annually used as filling material for mine cavities. At its lowest, the acidity of the waste ore had a pH of 2, causing corrosion problems for the machinery. Wastewater neutralization with waste lime started in 1964 to reduce the damage. In the late 1960s, waste-ore enrichment started again on a larger scale. Altogether, 508 800 kg of Co, Cu, Zn, S, Fe, Ni, Au, and Ag were recovered from the waste material between 1967 and 1980 [57].

In 1960, local landowners raised a charge against the Outokumpu mine because of the pollution of water courses. This led to long-lasting legal transactions and the payment of economic compensation by the company for polluting the watercourses [58]. At this point, the company realized the necessity of developing technology to protect the environment. The first environmental protection engineer was hired in 1972. The next year, the company established an environmental protection commission to enhance public relations [53].

The tailings area (MT1, 2, and 3 in Fig. 2b) comprises 140 ha and contains up to 9.5 Mt extractive waste, which in 1981 contained on average 0.143 % Cu, 0.106 % Zn, 0.060 % Co, 4.0 % S, and 6.3 % Fe [58].

In addition to the environmental load caused by the historical Outokumpu mines, the nearby Vuonos mine caused contamination. The dam of the impoundment of the Vuonos mine collapsed in January 1984, causing a 20-m-wide fault zone where 30 000 m³ of contaminated water was released into the surrounding terrain [59], resulting in

Fig. 2. An overview of the Outokumpu mining area. a) Locations of the Luikonlahti, Kylälahti, Vuonos, and the historical Outokumpu mines, including Keretti and Mökkivaara. The geochemical background levels of Ni and Cu in the Outokumpu mining district are greater than the average in Finland. The Ni concentration in the fine fraction of glacial till is indicated with color and the Cu content with circles of different sizes. b) Mine tailings areas (MT1–3) and water flow directions at Outokumpu (modified from [52]). Basemaps @National Land Survey of Finland and HALTIK (a Finnish Government Information Technology Center).

environmental damage.

In the 1990s, the tailings area MT2 and part of MT1 underwent extensive landscaping efforts (Fig. 2b). This involved covering the tailings with a 20-cm gravel layer, which was topped with a 10-cm layer of peat-sand mix in a 20:1 ratio. Additionally, a part of the area was modified into a golf course [60]. MT1 is still a water-filled pond and MT3 was covered with a 30–50-cm-thick layer of glacial till [21]. These landscaping efforts did not prevent water infiltration into the tailings and the consequent formation of AMD.

Part of the Outokumpu ore deposit has remained unexploited. The current mining project, called Hautalampi, has gone through the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) process and the company has applied for an environmental permit for the mining operation. The

Centre for Economic Development, Transport, and the Environment of Finland concluded that the project described in the EIA includes considerable uncertainties and the implementation would have several significant negative environmental impacts [61].

Oxidation of sulfide minerals is still causing acid mine drainage in the Outokumpu area. The low pH is accelerating the weathering of mine tailings and the release of SOEC. For example, in 2013, the pH of Outokumpu Pond was 2.5 [52]. Effluent waters from the western mine tailings impoundment are collected in a 3000 m² wetland area, where limestone and peat are placed to raise the pH and bind the SOEC. According to Tornivaara and Kauppila [52], water released to the Alimmainen Hautalampi Pond and from there to the River Ruutunjoki in 1996–2006 contained on average 24 mg/L suspended solids, 890 mg/L

Fig. 3. An aerial view of the Outokumpu area. Simplified representation of mine-derived pollutants that degrade the environmental state of Lake Sysmäjärvi due to surface water and groundwater contamination. Map data © modified from National Land Survey of Finland, CC BY 4.0.

sulfate, 69.7 mg/L Fe, 220 µg/L Cu, 1470 µg/L Zn, 605 µg/L Co, 490 µg/L Ni, and 1090 µg/L Mn. The average conductivity was 160 mS/m and pH 5.

Lake Sysmäjärvi initially recovered from acidification due to neutralization efforts initiated in 1964. However, in recent years, the pH has again declined following the cessation of liming of the waters in 2001 [62]. Groundwater flowing into the surface waters appears to be the primary source of acid drainage [62]. Additionally, the ongoing aeration of Lake Sysmäjärvi is contributing to the decrease in water pH [63]. Although the nutrient load from agriculture has increased, causing eutrophication of the lake, the ecological condition of Lake Sysmäjärvi is classified as acceptable [64].

Post-monitoring of the historical mine site is mandated to be conducted according to the program [65] approved by the Centre for Economic Development, Transport, and the Environment. The monitoring program is based on the environmental and water permit Decision No. 79/09/2 [66]. According to the program, the overflow waters of the former Keretti mine and the water used in mining operations must be treated so that the pH of the waters discharged to Alimmainen Hautalampi Pond and from there to the River Ruutunjoki is between 6.0–9.0, and the concentrations of selected metals and SO₄, calculated as quarterly averages, must not exceed the following limits at the Ruutunmylly sampling point (respective limit values in mg/L): Fe (8), Mn (0.6), Zn (1.3), Cu (0.3), Co (0.3), Ni (0.3), and SO₄ (300). Other recent sources of

environmental loading, in addition to former sulfide ore mining activities, are the Vuonos talc enrichment plant, the Outokumpu wastewater treatment plant, the mineral processing pilot plant, and the Viinijärvi fish farm. The Vuonos mining area contains three extractive waste areas, consisting of old sulfide ore wastes and new talc ore wastes. Fig. 3 provides a simplified representation of mine-derived pollutants that degrade the condition of Lake Sysmäjärvi through surface water and groundwater contamination. In the mapping of the Outokumpu mining waste areas, the environmental risk was assessed as due to SOEC-containing runoff water [51].

3.1.2. Contaminated soil in the present-day Outokumpu town center

The results of the sampling campaign demonstrated that extractive waste used in earthworks is still releasing SOEC into the environment. The poor protective structures (compared with modern standards) of the Keretti and Mökkivaara mining waste areas are presumably the principal reason, but the unknown amounts of relocated wastes used for urban construction and earthworks are certainly affecting the situation in the town center. No documents or previous systematic investigations were found that reveal the extent to which extractive wastes were used outside the waste areas in the town center, but monitoring of the quality of surface waters and groundwater gave a hint, as it revealed elevated SOEC levels.

Multiple *aqua regia* leachable elemental concentrations in the test pit

Fig. 4. Soil contamination in the Outokumpu town. Ni content of drilled soil samples, *aqua regia* leachable fraction, at different depths. The exceedance of a threshold value for nickel is marked with a yellow symbol (50.01–100 mg/kg), the lower guideline limit with an orange symbol (100.01–150 mg/kg), and the exceedance of the upper guideline value with a red symbol (150.01–380 mg/kg). Exceedance of the limit value 380 mg/kg marks the nickel contaminated soil as hazardous waste [67,68]. A full list of the threshold and guideline values of the Decree of the Government (214/2007) is presented in Appendix B. Basemap presents urban areas as grey, natural areas as white, fields as yellow, forests as green and surface water as blue. Roads and city streets are marked with grey lines. Basemap © National Land Survey of Finland.

samples presented in Appendix C exceeded the guideline values of the Decree of the Government on the assessment of soil contamination and the remediation need [28]. A full list of the threshold and guideline values as presented in [28] can be found in Appendix B. For example, the Cu content exceeded the upper guideline value of 200 mg/kg in all four samples taken from test pit 107, which is located near the old Mökkivaara mine and metallurgical plant. The highest Cu content was 2733 mg/kg at a depth of 1.5–2.5 m, where Cr, Zn, and Ni also exceeded the upper guideline limit. In addition, two samples taken from test pit 105 exceeded the lower and upper guideline values for Cu. The Ni content exceeded the lower guideline value in seven test pits and the upper value in six test pits, with the highest concentration being recorded in test pit 113 (0.4–1.0 m), namely 1914 mg/kg. In addition, this sampling point displayed high Co and Cr contents.

Drilled soil samples revealed high Cu and especially high Ni contents at multiple locations and depths (Fig. 4a–c, Appendix C). The S content exceeded 1 % at drilling points D143, D161, and D163. The S content is not included in [28], although it reflects the acidification potential. S concentrations in drill core samples are quite high compared to the threshold value for sulfur in permanent extractive waste, which is 0.1 %, or 1.0 % if the acid potential/neutralization potential ratio is higher than 3. The high SOEC and sulfur contents of some soil samples, together with the field observations, indicate that part of the extractive wastes produced by the Outokumpu mine have been disposed of outside the waste areas and used as landfill and construction material.

3.1.3. Contamination of groundwater and urban runoff waters in Outokumpu town center

The groundwater results revealed metal concentrations as expected

based on the geochemical results for the soil, since groundwater monitoring started in the area in the area. In the assessment of groundwater quality, environmental quality standards (EQS) according to [69] were used (Table 1) to evaluate the soluble SOEC contents of groundwater. There is no defined reference value for urban runoff waters in Finland. However, the quality of runoff water was compared with the results of a study performed by Airola and others (2014) on the quality of runoff water in Helsinki, the capital of Finland. Reference values for stormwater in urban areas are presented for comparison in Table 1. Water sampling locations are presented in Appendix D.

New groundwater monitoring wells G1 and G2 were installed in the course of the studies in places where groundwater flow was expected to be representative. Groundwater monitoring wells G3 and G4 were old groundwater monitoring wells. The background well G5 is located outside the town center. The Government Decree 1040/2004 environmental quality standard for Co, Ni, Zn, and SO₄ was exceeded in G3 and only that for Ni in G4. The well water samples displayed better quality, although the Ni content of samples W3 and W4 exceeded the Ni quality standard, and W5, taken in March, exceeded the Zn quality standard.

Runoff water samples (R1–R3) clearly exceeded the average urban runoff value for Co and Ni. Zn values were exceeded in R2 and R3 samples taken in November. In addition, the R1 November sample and both R3 water samples exceeded SO₄ values.

3.1.4. Health risks related to the mining waste deposited in the urban area of Outokumpu

Preliminary health risk assessment included exposure by unintentional ingestion of soil (separate assessment for depths of 0.0–0.5 m, 0.5–1.5 m, and >1.5 m) and ingestion of fungi, berries, and tap water, in

Table 1

Selected soluble sulfide ore extraction-related contaminants (SOEC) contents in groundwater (sampled from groundwater monitoring wells and dug wells in 2021–2022) and urban runoff waters compared with the groundwater environmental quality standard (EQS, [69]) and average runoff water content in the urban area of Helsinki, the capital of Finland. Locations of the sampling points are presented in Appendix D.

		pH	Co µg/L	Cr µg/L	Cu µg/L	Ni µg/L	Zn µg/L	SO ₄ mg/L
Groundwater EQS*			2	10	20	10	60	150
<i>Groundwater (G)</i>								
G1	Nov.	7.63	0.66	< 0.20	< 3	1.5	< 5	76
	March		1.5	< 0.20	< 4	2	< 5	99
G2	Nov.	7.26	< 0.15	2	< 5	1.3	35	54
	March		< 0.15	2.5	< 6	1.3	74	< 0.3
G3	Nov.	6.84	340	0.51	< 1	320	850	1900
	March	6.72	420	0.36	< 1	450	-	1900
G4	Nov.	7.65	0.62	< 0.20	< 1	21	< 5	76
	March	6.65	0.56	< 0.20	< 1	23	< 5	73
G5	Nov.	6.76	< 0.15	< 0.20	< 1	2	< 5	6.1
	March	6.72	< 0.15	< 0.20	< 2	2.1	< 5	9.8
<i>Dug wells (W)</i>								
W1	Nov.	7.52	0.29	< 0.20	5.1	0.85	11	5
	March	6.83	0.32	< 0.20	2.8	1	< 5.0	5.7
W2	Nov.	7.36	0.24	< 0.20	2.7	1.5	11	8.3
	March	6.81	0.53	0.21	3.6	1.8	12	13
W3	Nov.	7.16	0.15	0.84	2.2	18	17	12
	March	6.69	< 0.15	0.61	2.5	38	-	21
W4	Nov.	7.25	0.15	0.62	2.2	21	8.2	19
	March	6.81	< 0.15	1.4	< 1.0	30	-	24
W5	Nov.	7.45	< 0.15	1.7	11	0.77	40	1.4
	March	6.81	1.1	1.1	4.8	< 0.6	69	1.3
W6	Nov.	7.14	0.38	0.25	< 1	0.73	7.3	15
	March	6.65	0.37	0.57	< 1	1.1	< 5.0	21
Runoff waters in Helsinki urban area, average* *		7.2	1.1	6.1	18.4	4.5	53.1	24.8
<i>Runoff waters (R)</i>								
R1	Nov.	7.3	3.7	0.69	5.5	72	40	110
	March	7.6	3.7	0.61	6	20	20	3.9
R2	Nov.	7.7	3.7	0.21	12	46	77	71
	March	7.8	2	0.36	8.6	32	40	53
R3	Nov.	7.2	4.6	0.75	7.1	75	66	4.5
	March	7.3	5.8	0.77	14	120	-	47

* [69]

** [40]

addition to inhalation of dust. In the town center, the hazard quotient did not exceed the limit value of 1 for any of the assessed SOEC for adults in the unintentional ingestion exposure pathway. It should be noted that there is no official guideline regarding which depth should be considered as topsoil when estimating exposure through ingestion. However, exposure via ingestion of soil from below 0.5 m depth is unlikely to occur. Nevertheless, these calculations show that if soil excavated from below 0.5 m depth is to be reused in the area, it is unlikely to be suitable for use as topsoil in areas where it could be ingested (e.g., playgrounds, school yards).

In the areas with changing land use, the hazard quotient did not exceed the limit value of 1 for any of the assessed SOEC for adults or children in the unintentional ingestion exposure pathway, although in a situation where the maximum concentration of nickel was used for both drinking water and soil, HQ was > 1 . It should be noted that the highest nickel concentration found in soil samples is exceptionally high, and much higher than the median value for nickel in soil. Due to the possibility of a health risk to children, the highest allowable concentration of nickel in topsoil (0–0.5 m) was assessed to be 1100 mg/kg. This level should be taken into account when new residential areas are built.

Exposure by inhalation was considered to occur by inhaling dust particles in the study area. SOEC included in this exposure pathway were As, Cu, Cr, Ni, and Zn, and the considered dust particle size was PM10. The calculated SOEC concentrations in the PM10 particle-size dust were compared with the respective TCA values, which describe the highest concentration level without adverse effects. This level was only exceeded for nickel, but both arsenic and nickel concentrations exceeded their respective target concentrations. While this does not mean that adverse effects will occur, they are possible. The combined effect of exposure has been calculated for Co, Cr, Ni, and Zn, since they all have negative health effects on the respiratory tracts and lungs. The hazard index (HI) for the additive effect was calculated using the hazard quotients from the ingestion exposure route. The result was that for children, $HI > 1$ for both areas near roads (town center) and the new planning areas for all considered soil depths (0.0–0.5 m, 0.5–1.5 m, and > 1.5 m). The subsoil does not affect inhalation but could if relocated on the surface.

The samples for assessing the risk through dust inhalation were taken almost 15 years ago [31], and new legislation has since been introduced related to the health risk assessment. A more detailed study on dust exposure accompanied by a new sampling campaign is suggested to be undertaken.

In summary, the most important exposure pathway may be inhalation of dust and unintentional ingestion of soil, whereas exposure by ingesting berries and fungi in the study area is not significant. When the Ni concentration in topsoil (0.0–0.5 m) is below 1100 mg/kg, no health risks are expected to occur. As mainly children were found to be at risk in high-concentration areas through unintentional soil ingestion, it is recommended that the topsoil in newly built residential areas and children's playground areas should contain the studied SOEC only at concentrations below the local background concentrations in soil parent material or below the threshold values as described in the Government Decree of Finland 214/2007.

A more comprehensive sampling campaign, including playgrounds, gardens, parks, and other green spaces in the urban environment, and an investigation of the risks posed by dust and edible plants would be beneficial for a more comprehensive risk assessment. Groundwater flow patterns should be determined, and for streams, flow rates and their seasonal variations should be investigated. Runoff water studies should be conducted to determine the sampling time frame in relation to rainfall events.

3.1.5. Risk management of soil rich in sulfide ore extraction-related contaminants (SOEC)

Based on the *aqua regia* leaching results, the excavated soil was categorized into six classes, which define their final disposal or potential utilization. The classification is based on current Finnish legislation

concerning the assessment of soil contamination and remediation needs [28]. The placement, disposal, and reuse alternatives according to the current legislation were planned and classified into six categories (Fig. 5), namely 1: as hazardous waste soil material (to be treated, $pH < 6$, or potentially acid forming); 2: as hazardous waste soil material (no treatment); 3: as non-hazardous waste soil material (to be treated, $pH < 6$, or potentially acid forming); 4: as non-hazardous waste soil material (no treatment); 5: as uncontaminated soil material (to be treated, $pH < 6$, or potentially acid forming); and 6: as uncontaminated soil material (no treatment). More sustainable methods are being explored as alternatives to the conventional “dig and haul” approach. However, since some roads urgently require renovation, at least part of the contaminated soil will be removed using this straightforward method.

3.2. Historical mining towns and the risk to human health

Mining and metallurgical industries have a global history. Extraction and processing have been inefficient, especially during earlier times, and several tons of rock have been mined and processed to obtain small amounts of commodities. Large quantities of waste have been generated [4]. Historical mining areas, which operated before the modern environmental laws were established, pose challenges for local stakeholders in managing and raising awareness about soil contamination [70].

UNESCO has nominated some historical mining sites as World Heritage Sites. The UNESCO Industrial World Heritage includes 60 sites, of which 24 are mining-related [71]. Freiberg (Germany), Falun (Sweden), and Aljustrel (Portugal), presented here, are all mining heritage sites. This status protects the mining heritage of the area but may also create a hindrance to applying remediation measures that would endanger the historical monuments of mining. Nevertheless, many of these sites have undergone significant remediation measures to rehabilitate the environmental consequences of mining activities.

We focus in this paper on sulfide mining sites, since they cause acid mine drainage (AMD), which is one of the most severe environmental problems caused by mining. The specific focus is on the historical mining sites located adjacent to a town or a city. In Finland, the environmental impact of historical mining sites has been evaluated [21], and from the sulfide mines, only the Outokumpu mining area is situated in the direct vicinity of a town center. There are some 6000 residents in the town of Outokumpu, while in comparison, Freiberg in Germany has 40 000 inhabitants and Falun in Sweden has 37 000 (Table 2).

Table 2 provides an overview of the situation of some European historical mining towns that suffer from SOEC in soil. The Chilean and Chinese historical mining cities [22,23] are included as a reminder that the issue needs global solutions. The number of historical mining cities and towns of this kind containing contaminated soil is hundreds worldwide. Soil contamination arising from former mining activities continues to create a range of health and environmental concerns.

Next, we provide background information on Falun, Aljustrel, Lavrion, and Freiberg, presented in Table 2, to support the discussion section.

3.2.1. Falun, Sweden

Falun has many similarities to Outokumpu and offers a case study concerning the remediation measures suggested for the mine tailings area (see Section 4.2 above). The mine was a sulfide ore mine, the metal mined was copper and the town of Falun grew around the mine. In addition to placing the mine tailings in mine waste areas, they were placed all over Falun to fill in the wet areas [71]. Until 1987, acid mine drainage flowed freely to the Falu river without any treatment. The mine waste was deposited on the riverbank narrowing the river from 75 m to 15–25 m [75]. There are still 7 M m³ of mining wastes in the center of Falun [76]. Some of the waste is still visible as piles, forming part of the cultural heritage, while part is buried underground and beneath roads [75], as was also in carried out in Outokumpu.

The Falun mine operated for far longer than in Outokumpu, and the

Fig. 5. Disposal and utilization alternatives of contaminated soils in Outokumpu. Flowchart of the six classes for soil rich in sulfide ore extraction-related contaminants (SOEC) present in road fillings in Outokumpu town center. Flowchart is based on [27].

Table 2

Examples of historical mining towns and cities with environmental and health issues related to contaminants originating from sulfide ore extraction (SOEC). BCE = Before Common Era, CE = Common Era. A question mark indicates that the available information is uncertain or based on preliminary findings.

Historical mining town/city	Population/ total area (km ²)	Mining started	Main SOEC	Reported source of exposure	References
Outokumpu, Finland	6 409/584	1910 CE	Ni, Cu, Zn, S, Co, Cr	Soil ingestion, dust?	This paper, [72]
Freiberg, Germany	40 485/48	1100 CE	As, Cd, Pb,	Consumption of plants	[24]
Falun, Sweden	37 291/2040	1000 CE	Zn, Cd, Cu, Pb	Dust, soil ingestion?	Hanæus et al., 2010; [73]
Aljustrel, Portugal	9 257/458	3000 BCE	As, Cu, Cd, Pb, Sb, Zn	Dust, consumption of plants	Barroso et al. 2021; [74]
Lavrion, Greece	7 525/150	3500 BCE	Zn, Pb, As, Cu, Sb, Cd	Dust, consumption of plants	Demetriades, 1999
Tocopilla, Chile	25 000/4039	1915 CE	Cu, Zn, Pb	Dust	[22]
Daye, China	871 000/1566	0 CE	As, Cd, Cu	Consumption of plants, dust?	[23]

mine was closed in 1992 after over 1000 years of mining activities. The mining company (Stora) agreed to share the costs with the government of Sweden, which totaled SEK 166 M [75].

After closure, remediation measures were implemented [76]. The tailings pond in Falun was sealed with a soil cover to prevent discharges of Zn and Cd. The soil cover consisted of a 1-m-thick sealant layer made of fly ash and biosludge, applied in two 0.5-m-thick layers, and another 0.5-m protective layer of till and bark waste. After covering, discharges of Zn and Cd from the tailings pond were reduced by 80–95 %. Additionally, a system to collect and treat AMD was implemented near the Falun mine, respecting its status as a UNESCO World Heritage Site.

The Swedish Environmental Protection Agency provides a criterion limit of 50 mg/kg for lead in areas designated for sensitive use, meaning that both adults and children can live in the area for their lifetime. A limit of 400 mg/kg is set for less sensitive use. The whole city center of Falun contains over 300 mg/kg lead (see [75], Fig. 5). A health risk assessment project is being conducted in 2023–2024 to assess the risks associated with living in the Falun area [77]. The findings will serve as a basis for reviewing earlier recommendations related to various activities in the region, such as building, farming, and picking mushrooms and

berries.

3.2.2. Aljustrel, Portugal

Aljustrel is situated in the southwestern region of Portugal, in the western section of the Iberian Pyrite Belt (IPB). It contains six Cu- and Zn-rich deposits. After thousands of years of sulfide ore mining history, the extractive wastes are spread all over, causing severe AMD [78,79]. The Portuguese part of IPB also contains other historical mining sites, such as São Domingos, Lousal, and Caveira, where the state of the environment is a significant concern [74]. Candedias et al., (2010b) performed a soil sampling campaign of 356 samples over an area of 44 Km². The chemical measurements (hot aqua regia followed by ICP-ES) demonstrated that the content of As, Cd, Cu, and Zn in the topsoil exceeded the limit values set for Portugal and Andalusia. For example, the arsenic content in the soil is 3936 mg/kg at its highest, and the Cu content 5414 mg/kg.

A waste encapsulation solution for the disposal of SOEC-rich soil has been implemented in Aljustrel [74]. The remediation of a large, contaminated area included the removal of contaminated soil, piling of the soil in a restricted area nearby, and sealing it with limestone and

clay. Drainage channels were constructed to collect seepage and potentially acid drainage waters, which were guided to evaporation–concentration ponds and from there to wetlands, before being released to the natural watercourse. According to Alvarenga et al. [41], previous conventional remediation attempts have not been successful enough, and they suggest reducing the mobility and bioavailability of potentially toxic elements by applying assisted phytoremediation.

In addition to Aljustrel, several small mining towns are located on the Spanish side of the Iberian Pyrite Belt, such as El Campillo, Minas de Riotinto, and Nerva [80].

3.2.3. Lavrion, Greece

The mining history of the Lavrion area in Greece can be traced back to as early as 3500 BCE. The main product mined was argentiferous galena [81]. Mine tailings contain sulfide minerals causing acid mine drainage. In addition, highly toxic carbonate tailings exist over a large area in residential and public areas [82–84]. According to Demetriades [85], modern mining activities between 1865 and 1989 caused major damage to the environment, which led to widespread contamination of the soil by SOEC (e.g., lead, zinc, arsenic, antimony, cadmium, copper, mercury). This has contributed to elevated lead concentrations recorded in blood samples from children [85–87,82,88]. The lead content (hot *aqua regia* followed by ICP-ES) of the overburden is highly variable, being between 810 and 15 1579 mg/kg, with the mean content being 11587 mg/kg. Dust in the home environment appears to be a major concern related to health in the Lavrion area. The total Pb contents in the indoor dust of households vary from 488 to 18617 mg/kg [82,85], which is extremely alarming. In addition, direct contact with humans, unintentional ingestion, and the consumption of plants are seen as a health risk in the area [89,84,88]. Extensive investigations on the condition of the soil in the area have been conducted, but the proposed remediation actions have never been implemented [90].

Demetriades et al., 1999c have presented maps showing the locations of different types of mining wastes, along with plans for the necessary remediation measures for each waste area. Detailed maps of urban control zones (see Demetriades et al., 1999c, chapters 11 and 12) highlighting specific risks, are also included, similar to the approach taken in Freiberg. Additionally, a benefit index has been calculated for each area once the remediation measures are completed.

3.2.4. Freiberg, Germany

With a mining and ore processing history spanning over eight centuries, the Freiberg mining operators primarily extracted silver, often accompanied by arsenic in various forms, leading to significant As, Cd, and Pb pollution in the region [91,92].

In the current situation, the Freiberg area is an exemplary demonstration of comprehensive planning and soil management. It has been regulated as a Soil Planning Area (SPA), where limit values have been provided based on land use and exposure scenarios, for example, for playgrounds, parks and leisure areas, or agricultural land use [25]. In addition, regional handling and re-use of excavated soil materials is based on contamination categories to avoid extensive soil analysis, which was formerly slowing down urban development.

The implementation of an SPA Freiberg in 2011 was based on specific regulations in Germany (§ 21 [93]) and Saxony (§ 9 [94]), laid down for managing large areas of contaminated land. A general division was made between small but extremely contaminated sites (e.g., former mining shafts, ore processing and smelting sites, tailings) and moderate, but large-area contamination. The extremely contaminated sites have been managed and remediated site by site following the regular scheme for contaminated sites in Germany, laid down in BBodSchV [95], while all other parts of the region have been addressed by the SPA. Preparation for the SPA followed steps and methodology given by technical guidance [96]. Since the region was partly known and partly suspected to be highly contaminated due to mining activities, results from an intense soil investigation program (besides site-specific investigation on small

but extremely contaminated sites) have been used to establish a contaminant map service for the whole area [97]. Starting in 2003 it took five years and several field campaigns to collect altogether 2352 soil samples to establish a sampling density from 3.4 samples per km² at the outer parts of the region up to 35 samples per km² for Freiberg and its surrounding area for the SPA in the Freiberg region [98]. The depth of soil sampling followed German regulation [95]: for urban land use and agricultural grassland both, from 0 to 0.1 and 0.1–0.3 m and for arable land both from 0 to 0.3 and 0.3–0.6 m. The chemical analysis on As, Cd and Pb in soil also followed BBodSchV [95] by using DIN EN ISO 11885:04/98 (hot *aqua regia* extraction followed by ICP-OES/MS detection).

Based on the contaminant status and land use, specific threats have been identified to pose relevant risks:

- Direct contact and ingestion of contaminated soil by children
- Inhalation of contaminated soil dust
- Contaminant transfer on agricultural land into food and fodder crops
- Contaminant transfer in private garden plots into food
- Contaminated soil relocation to sites with lower contamination during construction activities
- Leaching of contaminants from soil to groundwater
- Erosion of contaminated soil or material and transfer into rivers

Contaminant classification was based on the statistical probability of exceeding the tolerable risk, referring to the concentration in soil for several land-use scenarios (i.e., playgrounds, residential areas, parks, and leisure facilities). If, for instance, the calculated probability was below 5 %, it was not considered necessary to enforce any action. A probability of up to 50 % was connected to soft management measures (see [99]), a probability of up to 95 % to more rigorous measures, and a higher probability to remediation procedures such as soil excavation or soil sealing (Fig. 6).

Some extremely contaminated sites, e.g., tailings, are directly located on the River Freiberger Mulde, where erosion has led to highly contaminated sediments followed by highly contaminated soils occurring in downstream alluvial plains due to flood events, such as in 2002 [100]. Measures to prevent erosion at these sites have proved successful, since the flood in 2013 resulted in relocated sediments that were much less contaminated compared to the 2002 flood [101]. The prevention of soil erosion from contaminated arable land was managed by a general agricultural support program to support dense vegetation cover, e.g., by reduced tillage [102].

Leaching of contaminants or AMD in the Freiberg region could be linked to specific tailings and former mining ditches, tunnels, and water channels, and is therefore treated site-specifically and not in general at the whole region level, where natural soil with a high contamination level has displayed a low leachate concentration [103]. Drinking water in the Freiberg region is produced by using water from large water dams in the upper mountains, fulfilling all the requirements of the EU drinking water directive. Dust from contaminated soil and sites and the related risks could mainly be connected to construction work in residential areas under dry weather conditions. This was addressed by administrative advice to keep soil and material wet during work and transportation by spraying with drinking water. All other threats from contamination in the Freiberg region have been fully addressed during the preparation of the Soil Planning Area (Fig. 7).

Even though the source of pollution is SOEC, the challenges faced in the Freiberg area differ geochemically from those in Outokumpu, where the contaminants are mainly Ni, Zn, Cr, and Co. Moreover, agriculture in the Freiberg area highlights the importance of investigating and preventing the transfer of metals and metalloids from soil to crops. Several (pre-)harvest analysis programs have been established to monitor SOEC concentrations in crops and guarantee compliance with EU regulations on food and fodder safety (e.g., [104]).

The risk assessment performed and updated at the Freiberg area,

Fig. 6. Soil Planning Area in the historical mining town of Freiberg, Germany. Ore veins, mining sites, and arsenic classification according to the probability (5 % green line, 50 % yellow line, and 95 % red line) of exceeding tolerable soil concentration in the Freiberg region.

based on numerous studies (e.g., [105-107,25,98]). Risk management in urban surroundings, such as playgrounds, housing areas, and parks, was based on the statistical probability of exceeding non-tolerable risk levels [25]. In addition, mine tailings and deposits of mine extractive wastes from a total of 9 sites with a combined volume of 7.3 million m³ and covering 4 km² have been categorized and remediated in a stepwise manner, offering an opportunity to re-collect waste and contaminated soil used in the region before final remediation involving a set of cover layers to avoid any contact and leaching. These sites have been prepared for industrial re-use or photovoltaic power installation.

Regularly updated risk management recommendations for farmers [108] include using plant species having low As and Cd uptake, pre-harvest evaluation of toxic elements in crops, and considering utilization in energy production for harvested crops exceeding limit values.

Repeatedly occurring exceedance of limit values may necessitate permanent land use changes. In addition, choosing the right type of fertilizer, using the proper amount of lime, enhancing the aeration of wet soil, and avoiding the disturbance of deeper soil layers are methods to reduce As uptake by crops. Nevertheless, it is essential to recognize that each site has unique characteristics and thus requires tailoring of case-specific risk management and solutions.

4. Discussion

We have compared the history, environmental conditions, and mining-induced health-related issues of five European historical mining towns: Outokumpu, Freiberg, Falun, Aljustrel, and Lavrion (Table 2). The historical mining cities of Daye, China, and Topochilla, Chile, are

Fig. 7. Implementation and regulation procedure in the Soil Planning Area of Freiberg.

mentioned as a reminder that the need for solutions is global. The situation in Freiberg and the research carried out in Outokumpu are explained in more detail, while the other mining towns have been briefly reviewed based on the literature. The mining environment in Outokumpu still requires additional studies. In contrast, the situation in Freiberg has been well studied and controlled, most contaminated areas have been remediated, and areas with acceptable contamination levels are used in a controlled and safe manner. The other mining towns represent situations that fall between those of Outokumpu and Freiberg. However, contents of harmful SOEC appear to be much lower in Outokumpu compared to the other sites. All the other mining towns are dealing with high content of arsenic or lead, both of which are highly toxic to humans and biota [109], which makes remediation actions more

urgent. When considering the five SOECs present at the reviewed locations (As, Pb, Cu, Ni and Zn), As and Pb are the primary concern for public health [110]. The historical mining towns cities presented are characterized by sulfide ore deposits, which have been mined for decades or even for thousands of years. This has led to massive amounts of sulfide-rich extractive waste. These wastes have been managed without understanding or consideration of their potential harmful effects to the environment and to human health. As a result, the waste material has caused acid mine drainage, dust containing harmful substances, and soil contamination in the surrounding environment.

4.1. Alternative solutions for the disposal of contaminated soils in Outokumpu

Historical mining activities in the Outokumpu town area have left a mark on the quality of soil and both groundwater and surface waters. Chemical analyses of soil and water samples revealed higher than average concentrations of, particularly, Co, Cr, Cu, Ni, and Zn compared with the average concentrations or regional background concentrations in Finland (gtkdata.gtk.fi/Tapir/; [111]). The results demonstrated how variable the soil quality is in the Outokumpu urban area. The soil may contain uncontaminated natural soil, soil with naturally elevated concentrations, soil contaminated with mining waste, with very high SOEC concentrations, or a mixture of these. The decision to use extractive waste in land construction now presents a convoluted problem, demanding a solution that is reasonable both economically and environmentally. A preliminary plan for SOEC-rich soil management has been developed, but details regarding how to execute the plan are still unclear. Increasing the local utilization rate in an environmentally safe manner and implementing best practice solutions that reduce final disposal costs are to be considered.

The characteristics of excavated soil significantly impact its placement or utilization possibilities. Some of the excavated materials may be suitable for use in fills or earthworks from a geochemical perspective. However, the soil materials must also be suitable for the intended use based on their other properties. For instance, factors such as frost susceptibility or corrosion properties need to be considered in geotechnical utilization (e.g., for street infrastructures). In the future, a small portion of metals could be recovered from excavated materials if mining and processing activities commence in the area. This scenario also depends on the development of technology and metal prices.

The solutions suggested for the management and placement of SOEC-rich soil materials necessitate extensive transportation, resulting in extra carbon dioxide emissions and substantial costs. The final disposal of SOEC-rich soil excavated during the renewal of the urban infrastructure is estimated to incur a cost of over €180 M during the next decade, and the evaluated costs concerning the next phase of road renovations are over €225 M. However, the actual costs associated with SOEC-rich soil materials could be even higher, since the data presented in this paper revealed the problem, but there is a need for additional sampling to properly address the remediation options.

The question is how to secure funding for this substantial remediation project and whether it is the most sustainable and economically reasonable way to deal with the situation. Another question is how to tackle other more striking environmental challenges in the area, such as the leaking mine tailings area, which is one of the main reasons for the degradation of the environmental condition of the protected Lake Sismajärvi (Fig. 3).

Mine tailings used in road construction are mixed with soil, resulting in a lower content of toxic elements than in disposed tailings. Therefore, disposing of road construction wastes in the old tailings area would not lower the quality of the waste. The potentially increasing SOEC load in surface water and groundwater discharging from the tailings area should be considered. It is apparent that the issue of the leaking bottom lining of the tailings pond needs to be addressed in any case in the future.

The permeable foundation of the Outokumpu tailings area is hardly repairable any longer. However, implementing a modern cover structure following the best practices of the extractive industry [112] would prevent further oxidation and SOEC release from the mine tailings to the surrounding surface and groundwaters. This type of cover structure would include several functional layers, preventing oxygen and rainwater flow to the underlying mine tailings and groundwater.

A multilayered dry soil cover placed on top of the extractive waste would decrease hydraulic conductivity, preventing meteoric water from entering the waste and thus reducing the oxidation of sulfide minerals and the formation of AMD. The most complex structure contains, from top to bottom, a vegetative layer, topsoil layer, drainage layer,

geotextile, barrier layer, coarse texture layer, fine-textured layer, and another coarse texture layer on top of the waste. A more specific description is provided in the Best Available Techniques (BAT) Reference Document for the Management of Waste from Extractive Industries by Garbarino and others (2018) in the section on permanent covers. According to Garbarino and others (2018), the typical thickness of a multilayered cover is between 0.5 and 3.0 m, and the hydraulic conductivity of the impermeable layer is generally less than 10^{-9} .

When calculating the costs, we can compare the Outokumpu case with the costs of the recent closure of the Hitura nickel mine in western Finland, which were altogether €23 M. The Hitura mine tailings area covers 117 ha [113], which is close to the size of the Outokumpu tailings area (140 ha). The excavation and transportation of contaminated soil to the mine tailings area will still incur costs, and temporary covering of the area until enough contaminated soil has been transported to the area would need to be considered.

The proposed disposal of contaminated soil in the mine tailings area and the implementation of a new tailings cover structure may not be a viable solution if metal recovery from the tailings is considered in the near future or if current plans for primary ore extraction and waste disposal are pursued. In such a scenario, the mining company exploiting the deposit would be responsible for managing the establishment of modern tailings storage facilities and the implementation of proper closure measures after exploitation.

Encapsulation of the SOEC-rich soil, as has been implemented in Aljustrel [74], or stabilization with a binder [114], and placing the material in the old waste areas of Outokumpu could be considered. This scenario would not resolve the overall SOEC problem, but it could be a better solution compared to the situation where contaminated soil is transported over long distances and disposed of at landfill sites outside the mining brownfield area.

When considering a comprehensive solution to restrain the SOEC contamination at Outokumpu, we suggest nominating the region, similarly to Freiberg, as a 'Soil Planning Area', a designated land-use area, covering smaller areas categorized according to the land-use purpose and the corresponding threshold values for contaminants allowed to avoid transporting and disposing of contaminated soil in areas outside the mining region.

There is a growing call for legislative flexibility in the context of remediating mining cities, such as Outokumpu. It is essential to reconsider the relevance of the conventional approach of removing, transporting, and disposing of contaminated soil in a landfill, especially when planning the new soil directive approach for cities in the vicinity of historical mines. Instead, we should seek more comprehensive solutions and examine the possibility of managing disposal within the brownfield and implementing tailored remediation measures that improve the environmental condition of the area on a larger scale.

Based on the preliminary risk assessment study, unintentional ingestion and dust inhalation are the primary routes of exposure to harmful substances in Outokumpu. Edible plants may have a greater impact than estimated due to the incomplete data used in the risk assessment. Soil samples sent for analysis were selected based on high metal concentrations (using a portable XRF analyzer). When only samples with high metal levels are analyzed, the result will be overestimated metal content. This exaggerates the overall picture of concentrations. Overall, the risk assessment is incomplete, and further research is needed. Therefore, we refer to the risk assessment study as a preliminary risk assessment.

4.2. Toward a global framework for the remediation of mining towns and cities

The EU's Soil Mission aims to improve soil health by raising awareness and promoting sustainable land use. The aim is also to establish 100 Living Labs [115], bringing together stakeholders from various sectors to develop innovative solutions to improve soil health. The EU aims to develop policies and regulations to help member states to

achieve soil protection goals. Currently, the EU has no regulation concerning soil health, although individual countries have their own regulations and guidelines/limits regarding soil management. The EU has proposed a Soil Monitoring Law, comparable with earlier regulations established to protect air and water. Among other measures, the proposal will require member states to manage soil contamination (e.g., [71]).

We urge the recognition of historical mining towns as distinct entities that require specific regulation, and we suggest considering a European-wide or even global approach for managing the contaminated soils first, in a similar comprehensive manner as has been implemented, for example, in Freiberg. Establishing Soil Planning Areas for historical mining towns might offer economically, socially, and environmentally reasonable case-specific solutions.

The situation created by historical mining of sulfide ores is problematic in multiple ways. In addition to creating health issues due to the pollution of waterways, soils, and air, the environmental issues also reduce the value of properties and the overall viability of the area [116]. The remediation measures in historical mining towns might increase the value of properties. For example, Nilsson and Östberg [75] found that in the Falun area, real estate prices increased by 6.9 % after implementing remediation measures compared to properties located outside the remediated area. They evaluated that this increased the combined value of the properties by over SEK 100 M (c.a. USD 9.1 M \$ at the current rate). This covers and even exceeds the governmental remediation costs for the area. Nevertheless, it is not evident that property prices will increase after remediation measures, as was shown by Kiel and Williams [117], because the effect varies from site to site.

In our opinion, Outokumpu and other mining towns with contaminated soils and poorly managed mining wastes could benefit greatly from learning about the high-quality soil contamination and risk assessment studies conducted in the Lavrion area in Greece (e.g. [85,86,90]). Unfortunately, despite the valuable dataset produced in the Lavrion area, it has not been used to address the situation, even though the authors strongly appeal to decision makers in their reports. While a high-quality study can contribute to advancing the issue, it is insufficient on its own to ensure the implementation of measures to resolve the issue. To effectively address the matter, widespread political will and binding legislation are required that mandates action to resolve the environmental and health issues caused by historical mining.

The current legislation in Finland and Sweden, for example, is not flexible in dealing with large-scale contamination that does not represent geochemical background concentrations but requires a site-specific risk assessment for all sites, which demands considerable resources. According to Finnish Waste Act 646/2011, excavated contaminated soils must be treated as waste, unless during the time of excavation, there exists an identified possibility for re-use, and the soil material is tested to be suitable for that purpose and risk assessment for the reuse case shows there will be no risk to human health or environmental risk. The permitting process for reusing contaminated soil might take a long time and incur costs in the form of temporary storage of materials, transporting contaminated soil, laboratory testing and needed consultancy. If there is no immediate possibility for reusing the soil material, it is taken to a landfill for contaminated soil. Landowners may also prefer the landfill option due to saved costs in the remediation process due to faster finalizing. However, this may not always be the most practical or environmentally optimal solution, and consumes more natural resources than the reuse option, as the excavated areas must be refilled with newly excavated soil from elsewhere. The approach to excavated contaminated soil reuse is similar e.g. in Sweden. The current legal framework does not allow other approaches.

Especially problematic this is for old mining towns, where the soil is considered contaminated for large areas, and remediation costs would be high regarding the town's economical size and ability to pay for the remediation. Remediating all areas might also threaten historical, architectural, and cultural values of the town, if demolition of historical

buildings was needed for a comprehensive remediation of the whole area.

5. Conclusions

The historical activities of the mining and metallurgical industries carried out before modern environmental legislation and regulations have dispersed potentially toxic elements and compounds into the environment. Waste rock piles and tailings dams consisting of a mixture of solids and liquids have been left on site, and proper mine closure actions have not been carried out at most of the sites. Surface waters and groundwater have been contaminated, in addition to soil. The inhalation of dust particles containing potentially toxic elements is also a significant exposure route. Globally, thousands of old mine sites revealed by open cuts, tailings, waste rock dumps, waste ponds, and processing infrastructure have been mapped with satellite images. In addition, soils contaminated by historical mining have had harmful impacts on wildlife. In Europe, the issue of historical mining towns is highlighted due to the proposal for an EU Soil Monitoring Law. What would be a sensible way to remediate a populated but contaminated area?

The on-site study performed in the historical mining town of Outokumpu in Finland revealed severe contamination of the soil in the town center due to the utilization of mine tailings as a road construction material. The highest Cu content measured from drill core samples was 2733 mg/kg at a depth of 1.5–2.5 m, where Cr, Zn, and Ni also exceeded the upper guideline limit. A preliminary risk assessment suggests possible health issues through the inhalation of dust and unintentional soil ingestion. Mine tailings have been mixed with soil, which makes the remediation measures complicated, not to mention the high costs of removal operations for contaminated soil. Another issue to consider is the 140-ha mine tailings area in the vicinity of the town center, which has been built without a protective lining and lacks a proper cover structure to prevent acid mine drainage.

In addition to Outokumpu, we have presented the situation in other historical mining towns, where populations have grown around sulfide mines and are facing similar consequences of former mining activities. In Falun, Sweden, and Lavrion, Greece, the most concerning metal appears to be Pb, while arsenic presents challenges in mining-affected areas of Freiberg in Germany and Aljustrel in Portugal. In the Outokumpu area Pb and As are not presenting an issue. Instead, Cu, Ni, and Zn pose the primary concerns.

The risk management and regulation procedures developed for Freiberg in Germany, the so called 'Soil Planning Area' concept, are suggested to be considered for Outokumpu in Finland and similar mining towns elsewhere as a first step for solving the environmental issues. Risk areas could be identified based on soil quality studies and threshold levels set for metals that pose risks to the environment and human health. Based on this, land use can be planned in a safe and controlled manner.

We propose the development of a global guidebook describing an appropriate approach for conducting soil sampling campaigns in historical mining towns to investigate soil contamination. For this purpose, acceptable sampling and research methods need to be defined, incorporating insights from earlier high-quality studies where applicable. Additionally, threshold values for substances hazardous to health should be established, and tailored to the intended uses of the soil, which include agricultural, industrial and residential use. In this context, it is essential to evaluate how legislation in different countries aligns with the development and implementation of the Soil Planning Area concept. Implementing the concept is the first step in a holistic remediation approach in historical mining towns.

The lessons learned can hopefully be applied in other historical mining towns and cities facing comparable challenges worldwide. The 'Soil Planning Area' regulation procedure provides a general approach to resolve issues related to contaminated mining-related soil in urban areas with a comprehensive package of tools to tackle environmental and health risks with reasonable economic resources.

Environmental Implication

Our EU project ISLANDR “Information-based Strategies for Land Remediation” is sustainable in environmental, economic, and social aspects, promoting ecological and human health. The urban mining environment management proposal we recommend provides a comprehensive solution that can be effectively implemented in mining towns and cities worldwide. Alternatively, doing practically nothing due to high costs could leave the mining environment in its current state, continuing to cause economic, social, and environmental disadvantages.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Soili Solismaa: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Kirsti Loukola-Ruskeeniemi:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Kristiina Nuotimäki:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology. **Hanna Tolvanen:** Writing – original draft, Investigation. **Kimmo Järvinen:** Writing – original draft, Investigation. **Ingo Müller:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. General assumptions used in risk assessment. Values are the same for depths 0.0–0.5 m, 0.5–1.5 m, and > 1.5 m

Variable	Value				Unit	Explanation	Reference
	Road area		Land use change area				
	Child	Adult	Child	Adult			
EF _{soil}	210	210	210	210	d / a	Exposure frequency	Estimate
EF _{fungi}	10	10	10	10	d / a	Exposure frequency	Estimate
EF _{berries}	365	365	365	365	d / a	Exposure frequency	Estimate
IR _{soil}	0.0001	0.00005	0.0001	0.00005	kg / d	Intake rate of soil	Estimate, reference 39
IR _{fungi}	0.002	0.046	0.002	0.046	kg / d	Intake rate of fungi	3
IR _{berries}	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.03	kg / d	Intake rate of berries	3
IR _{dust}	100	100	100	100	µg / d	Inhalation rate of dust	5
ED	6	34	6	34	a	Exposure duration	Estimate
BW	15	70	15	70	kg	Body weight	Estimate
AT	2190	12410	2190	12410	d	Time, over which the exposure is averaged	Estimate
ADD _{soil ingestion}	Varies	Varies	Varies	Varies	mg/kg / d	Average daily dose via soil ingestion	Calculated based on detected max. concentration
ADD _{fungi}	Varies	Varies	Varies	Varies	mg/kg / d	Average daily dose via fungi ingestion	Calculated based on detected max. concentration
ADD _{berries}	Varies	Varies	Varies	Varies	mg/kg / d	Average daily dose via berry ingestion	Calculated based on detected max. concentration
ADD _{water}	Varies	Varies	Varies	Varies	mg/kg / d	Average daily dose via water consumption	Calculated based on detected max. concentration
TDI	Depends on the element, see below	-	-	-	mg/kg / d	Tolerable daily intake	1
HQ	Varies per element and child/adult	-	-	-	-	Hazard quotient	Calculated

TDI values used for elements in the risk assessment in mg kg⁻¹ d⁻¹:

As	0.001	Pb	0.0018
Co	0.0014	Ni	0.012
Cr	0.005	Zn	0.5
Cu	0.14		

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- 1) SY 23/2007
- 2) OH 6/2014
- 3) FinRavinto 2017 research
- 4) RIVM 2007

5) <https://www.u-earth.eu/post/how-much-pollution-breathe-every-day>

6) OPASNET mine site area risk assessment

Appendix B. Threshold and guideline values for contaminating substances in soil according to Finnish [28] (VNa 214/2007). Selected elements relevant to the Outokumpu case study. The guideline values are defined based on either ecological risks (e) or health risks (t). If the risk for groundwater contamination is already higher than usual at lower concentrations than the lower guideline value, these substances are marked with the letter p

Element (symbol)	Natural concentration ¹ mg/kg	Threshold value mg/kg	Lower guideline value mg/kg	Upper guideline value mg/kg
Metals and metalloids²				
Cobalt (Co) (p)	8 (1–30)	20	100 (e)	250 (e)
Chromium (Cr)	31 (6–170)	100	200 (e)	300 (e)
Copper (Cu)	22 (5–110)	100	150 (e)	200 (e)
Nickel (Ni)	17 (3–100)	50	100 (e)	150 (e)
Lead (Pb)	5 (0.1–5)	60	200 (t)	750 (e)
Zinc (Zn)	31 (8–110)	200	250 (e)	400 (e)

1) The median values and ranges for natural concentrations for the fine matter in moraine defined through *aqua regia* extraction. In site-specific assessments, it must be noted that especially in clays the natural concentrations can be notably higher than those measured in moraine.

2) The guideline values for metals and metalloids defined on ecological grounds are derived by adding the calculated concentration describing acceptable ecological risk to the average concentration in the natural mineral soil. The natural concentrations in soil, if defined in a reliable manner, can be taken into account in site-specific assessments in a similar manner.

Appendix C. *Aqua regia* leachable elemental concentrations and locations of test pit and drill core samples

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.jhazmat.2024.136962](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2024.136962).

Appendix D. Water sampling locations in the town center of Outokumpu in 2021–2022 (this study)

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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